

Influence of Stress on Administrators' Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

The study examined influence of stress in administrators' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. To achieve the purpose of the study the researcher formulated three (3) objectives of the study, research questions and hypotheses that guided the study. The researcher made use of descriptive survey design for the research design. The population of the study consists of all the administrators, vice administrators and head of department in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis with a population size, of 800. The study made use of simple random sampling techniques for the sample and sampling technique with a sample size of 400 administrators Vice administrators and HODS. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire. The data gathered were analysed using mean score and standard deviation for the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using z-test statistical tool at a 0.05 level of significant. Based on the analysis, the findings of the study revealed that there is a negative significant relationship between sources of administrators' stress and their job performance in public senior secondary schools, instructional supervision as a stressor influence the school administrators' job performance in public senior secondary schools and that lack of finance or funds has a negative influence on school administrators job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that government through the ministry of education should organize awareness programme for all the school heads or administration to enlighten and educate them on sources of stress hence it affects or influence their job performance, the duty of instructional supervision should not be limited to the school administrators to avoid work overload hence it may influence their job performance and government through ministry of education should take seriously the issue of facilities procurement and maintenance to help the school administrators since it influence their job performance.

INTRODUCTION

Stress had been defined as a condition of being subject to external forces or pressures and can either be positive/pleasant (eustress) or negative/unpleasant (distress) (Willis 2015). Stress could also be defined as the body's reaction to any change that requires an adjustment or response. The body reacts to these changes with physical, mental and emotional responses. Scholars also observed that stress is a normal part of life. You can experience stress from your environment, office, job, etc. Stress slows normal bodily functions, such as the digestive and immune systems. The condition that causes stress can either be pleasant or unpleasant. These conditions are attributed to occupational, socio-economic and political challenges of life which include everything both inside and outside the body that challenges an individual to adapt to such situations. They can either be physical such as heat, cold, and noise or emotional such as fear, anxiety and depression. Psychologists presuppose that personality differences influence the levels of stress in ones life. They have identified and classified two basic personality types; A and B. Type A are hyperactive, aggressive, super ambitious, hard driving, and tend to have a short fuse while type B are composed, relaxed, less ambitious and easy going.

Numerous studies have documented statistical data on occupational stress related incidences. The United Kingdom's (UK) Health and Safety Executive (HSE) acknowledges that the top seven stressed professionals are administrators, nurses, managers, social workers, road transport drivers, police officers and prison officers (Willis, 2015). The typically overstressed person being a non-white male or female administrator aged 35-44 years. Furthermore, the Guardian Financial Services of UK ranks professions according to stress levels. The Guardian Financial Services survey indicated that 500,000 workers in the UK suffer from work related stress; 150,000 have taken at least a month sick off due to work related stress and altogether 6.5 million sick days/offers were taken each year under stress related incidences. It was estimated that every day, 270,000 people take time off for stress related illnesses at a cost to the economy of £10.2 billion annually.

In Nigeria, school administrators are faced with teaching, instructional programmes and administrative tasks which include: curriculum and instructional programmes, finance and business, staff, students, physical resources and public relations. These tasks being peculiar cause prolonged accumulation of stress which results in burnout; a state of emotional and physical exhaustion which reduces productivity and saps energy. Burnout intern causes emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and low personal accomplishment (Otieno, 2018).

Stress related burnout is a real threat to business administrators, administrators and workers. In a study conducted among entrepreneurs, more than half of those surveyed said they experience high levels of stress and extreme fatigue, 46% said they come to work one to four days a year when they are too stressed to be effective. (Barclays Bank Magazine, 2016). The Seed (2018), while analyzing the causes of violent student riots in Secondary

schools notes that head administrators (administrators) are overworked and suffering from stress caused by inability to raise issues for fear of job loss or vindictive transfer, lack of support from superiors, parents and political establishment, the plague by anonymous letters, rumours and innuendo.

Concept of Stress

Various writers, researchers, authorities have seen stress from different and diverse perspective. This chapter is set to review what they have written about stress and make valuable contributions to the study. The word “stress” like ‘success’, ‘failure’, ‘happiness’ means different things to different people so that defining it to a layman is extremely difficult though it has become part of our daily well know researcher in the field of medicine, Selye (2016) defined stress as “the non-specific response of the body to any demands made upon it”. According to him “stress is not merely a synonym for distress”. Medical researches according to Selye (2014) have shown that the body responds in stereotyped manner with identical biochemical changes essentially meant to cope with many types of increased demands upon the human machinery. Selye (2014) describes stress as physical and physiological reaction of the body demanding stimulus events. According to Emerenini (2015) in an unpublished work on Low back pain.

Hall (2021) saw stress as, “an external force operating on a system, be that system an organization or a person”. This agrees with Ezeilo (2015) who saw stress as, pressure from an adverse force or influence that imposes unusual demands on an organism”. Stress occurs when there are demands on a person which tax or exceed the person’s adjustive resources. In many modern organization, (schools), managers and professionals are faced with various forces. These forces range from ambiguity, irrational behaviour and stress to societal changes such as accelerated technological development, knowledge revolution and societal structures. All these create a complex environment full of anxiety, conflicts, frustration, indifference, apathy, dismay and tension. According to Osgood (2018), a large number of managers and professionals in organizations (school) find themselves in a type of environment full of conflicts, indifference apathy and frustrations, and these create stress and strains on their systems.

Causes, Sources and Influence of Stressors

There are stressors to virtually every occupation and business. Kane (2017) classifies stressors into two categories: acute and chronic. Acute stressors are the reaction to the immediate threat (fight or flight) response caused by noise, danger, over-crowding, bullying or harassment. Chronic stressors are pressures which are ongoing and continuous when the urge to fight or flight has been suppressed such as ongoing pressurized work, ongoing relationship problems, isolation and persistent financial worries.

Numerous studies have identified the major causes of stress and burnout in the service industry as work conditions that employees such as administrators, police, managers and prison warders are exposed to. Work overload, conflicts between workers and management, role ambiguity, difficult interpersonal relationships, roll over load, customer

contact, social support, job autonomy and locus of control were cited as major causes of stress and burnout among administrators, hoteliers, emergency health care service providers and professional residential service workers. Willis (2015) enumerates stressors as self centeredness, hate, worry, guilt feelings, envy, over sensitivity, sorrow, resentment, jealousy, fear, frustration and desire for approval.

According to Chapman, (2017), the typical causes of stress at work include bullying or harassment, feeling powerless and uninvolved in determining one's own responsibilities, continuous unreasonable performance demands, lack of effective communication and conflict resolution, lack of job security, long working hours, excessive time away from home and family, office politics and conflict among staff, a feeling that ones reward is not commensurate with ones responsibilities, working hours, responsibilities and pressures disrupting life-balance (diet, exercise, sleep and rest, family time). These conditions described suites the characteristics of Kenyan administrators meaning the administrators are working under stress. Head administrators“ administrative, teaching and management tasks changes with time in relation to change in environment challenges. This poses to head administrators which accumulate pressures from time to time. If the pressure is not well handled, the head administrator will suppress it for sometimes. Threat from below, middle aged crisis etc”

Some of these forces are the under discussed:

a) Indiscipline in the school: Indiscipline has been identified as a stressor and as such one of the sources of stress on managers Eferakeya (2013) contend that; indiscipline connotes anti-social deviant, and deviant behaviours which tends to, or relegate the integrity of the social order. Establishments and institutions such as secondary schools and colleges, even industries have codes or regulations that prescribe or proscribe the behavioural traits by members. Also Farrant (2020) has it that “Indiscipline among students is a stressor”. Indiscipline in secondary schools in Nigeria today occur in form of examination malpractice, truancy, disobedience, wickedness, willful destruction of property, sex offences, riotous behaviour, drug offences etc. All these and more have serious influence on the managerial efficiency of the school manager. Offence of various types visible in the various institutions of learning with particular reference to secondary school are all counted as indiscipline.

b) Exorbitant work demands: Many middle aged managers and some professional employees often find themselves faced with a punishing workload due to their involvement in many things at the same time. Thus, they are the heads of establishments, managers and administrators of corporate organizations, church leaders, people who own business, enterprises etc. By virtue of their leadership and executive roles and responsibilities they are charged with day to day policy decision making groups and organizations they head. According to Nweze (2014), the peculiarity of executive life experience is that their daily activities are usually fully packed with the pursuits of management and administrative chores as they struggle to ensure the goals of the organization and their personal visions. In addition, they have to keep pace with the

rapidity and requirements of hard, costly and risky decision and policies. The risk of non-realization or miscarriages of the policies rests on their shoulders. They combine their administrative roles and responsibilities in the office (school) with these incumbent on them as heads of families, church leaders and leaders in their smaller groups and communities.

c) Cultism and incessant riots: Terrorism is fast becoming the order of the day in our society today. The scenario is carried into our secondary schools today. Students from secret cults where the action of the members range from stealing, killing, raping, kidnapping etc. They also engage in other barbaric acts capable of derailing academic programmes because they are lazy and are not ready to work. In most schools today, students do not reason before they act over a little issue. According to Ezeilo (2015), stress is viewed as the subjective experience of students when events associated with his/her student status interact with the students personal characteristics to change his/her psychological and or physiological conditions. The riotous behaviour of students according to a pilot study of Ezeilo (2015), “are students attempt to cope with stress”.

d) Conflicts Within Organization: Inter-group or interpersonal conflict is an inevitable part of organizational life. In a school as an organization, conflicts abound among administrator themselves, between administrator and students, and between administrator and the Government, as well as between administrator and the administrators. In case of conflict between administrator and students, most administrator have a wrong notion of what discipline is and as a result, they give corrective measures without proper study of the situation. Griffith (2021) opined that, “A teacher has to study a situation before giving out a corrective measure.”

Failure to study the situation properly before giving a corrective measure often leads to conflict between the administrator and the students. Also the intervention of most parents in the affairs of students and administrator often brings in conflict between the administrator and the students. Conflict might also arise between the teacher (workers/staff) and the administrator. Such things like discrimination, oppression, lack of delegation of authority to the appropriate person and lack of justice often leads to conflicts between the administrator and the administrators. As the British imperial philosopher, Allison (2017) put it, Justice is the bond of society and no association of human individuals could be sustained without it. Most administrators of schools today are the, architects of most conflicts (stressors) in their schools.

e) The nature of school building and lack of school equipment and facilities: In some schools, the nature of the school building is nothing to write home about. Some are so dilapidated that staying under them is stressful in itself, while in some schools, there are not enough buildings to accommodate the school population that is large. Some are so badly structured and lack proper ventilation, such as installation of fans or air conditioners which s necessary for one to teach or learn for better understanding. Again, in some

schools there are no laboratories, libraries and sports facilities, even where they exist, they lack the ' necessary things that makes learning easy.

f) Inappropriate Leadership Style: According to Arbor (2021), "The leadership style of a superior can become a source of stress (a stressor) to himself/herself or for his/her subordinates." An authoritarian and hostile leader might create more psychological pressure that can influence his subordinates negatively and so create communication gap that will affect managerial process of the organization. According to Willis (2015), "a superior who employs laissez-faire, non-directive leadership style might create stress for the individual who is dependent on the structure." In other word both the authoritarian 'leadership style and the laissez-faire styles are stressors and so influence both the superior who employs them and the subordinates for whom they were employed

g) Non-payment/Delayed Payment of Administrators Salary

Be it as it may, the frustration, regrets and the inferiority complex that goes with teaching profession especially in Nigeria is a stressor in itself. The Government's inability to make teaching profession attractive has led to not only lack of job satisfaction among administrator but also to low esteem for those involved. Showing his abhorrence for the teaching profession, Lawrence (2020) wrote: I was, but am no more, thank God a schoolteacher. I dreamt last night I was teaching again - that is the only bad dream that ever affects my existence. Little or no prestige is within the means of a person who must exist solely on teacher's salary in Nigeria. In Nigerian status oriented society, this can cause a teacher to feel unsuccessful, at least in terms of material possession. So some administrator are forced to engage in some businesses to supplement their meagre income. Such businesses often result into the administrator being absent from the school, lack of lesson preparations and negligence of duty on the part of the teacher. This type of situation often leads to query writing by the administrator as well as strained relationship between the teacher and the administrator.

h) Life Change: Any change in life that requires a person to adapt to new circumstances can be stressors themselves regardless of whether or not the change is beneficial. For instance, the arrival of a new baby is an event usually anticipated with joy; but in this case it is regarded as a stressor because it causes numerous re-adjustments in the lives of both parents. Studies of personal histories suggested that physical and emotional disorder tend to cluster around period of major changes. Life Event Scale, studies using this method have it that Life changes scores totaling 300 or higher are associated with an increased frequency of various illness, psychological disorders, athletic injuries and even traffic accidents. However, other researchers have questioned this conclusion for the following reasons: one of which is Life Event Scale (LES), which assumes that change per pay is stressful.

i) The Nature of School Building and Lack of School Equipment and Facilities:

In some schools, the nature of the school building is nothing to write home about. Some are so dilapidated that staying under them is stressful in itself. While in some schools,

there are no enough buildings to accommodate the school population that is large. Some are so, badly structured and lack of ventilation so that installation of fans or air conditioners is necessary for one to teach or learn and understand better in them. Again, in some schools, there are no laboratories, libraries and sports facilities even where they exist, they lack necessary things that makes earning easy. According to UNICEF/SPEC assisted training workshop for head administrator in Rivers state October (2015) ‘inadequate school plant and equipment makes the management of the school difficult for the head teacher’ We find out that a school with little or no school facilities such as classroom blocks, science blocks, dormitory blocks etc facilities has a lot of managerial problems than that which has all or most of the facilities. Thus, a administrator in such a school with little or no facilities and equipment has high-level management problem and thus high level of stress.

j) Stress Induced by the Individual: Sometimes individual’s internal conflicts or problems form sources of stress and therefore stressors According to Osgood (2018), Thwarted ambition and goals are the causes of many psychosomatic reactions. Men and women suffer psychological stress from failure to be promoted. Even when their financial needs are satisfied at their present level, they feel bad if their level of responsibility do not tally with their qualifications. The same is applicable to most administrators of our schools today and this result is usually negative reaction that brings managerial inefficiencies. Compulsive eating is another source of stress for the executive.

k) Obsessive Concern for Work: Desire for vertical mobility sometimes reaches obsessed proportions. Nweze (2014) has it that “when a desire for work reaches obsessive proportion, it becomes a stressor.” Individuals obsessed with work operate under a high level of stress, pressure and conflict. Time and efforts expended by these people on their jobs far exceed the demands placed upon them by the organization. According to Friedman in Osgood (2018) “Obsessive devotion to work does not inevitably lead to the most productive output.” When a administrator is obsessed with work, he/she wants to see and do all the works in the nukes and corners of the school, he may lose the substance of the actual school management and this may lead to inefficiency.

l) Career Versus Family Demands: Work addicts as have been described above experience conflicts to some extent because personal and family life interferes with their work. Many managers and professionals experience conflicts because work and family place overlapping demands upon their time. As a result conflict occurs and thus stressors multiply. Attempt to devote equal attention to both often leads to inefficiency at managerial levels.

m) Threat from Below: Researches conducted by management experts suggested that younger men/women armed with modern management decision making tools are perceived as a threat by managers in the United States. Hall (2021) states that: You aspire

all your life to the mahogany paneled office, when you finally get close enough taste success, they tear out the paneling and put a computer and a damn MBA in space. In some schools today, the vice administrators are 100% more qualified and more knowledgeable than the administrators and so, the administrators often times feel being threatened by the presence of such a vice and this induces stress that comes from jealousy and insecurity.

n) Time Management: The issue of stress can also be seen among people who do not see time as something to direct their actions and movement. The concept of time management is an approach of good management of demands being made on us by virtue of our roles and responsibilities. The management according to Kane (2017) means Grouping the demands being made into “key result areas” so that they make sense”. It also requires concentrating on priorities so that attention is focused on fewer demands. Time management according to Ezeilo (2015) helps the individual manager or business executive take stock of his or her workload, identify the priorities and as such become better placed to cope with the multiplicity of pressures and demands on his/her time and resources. Some school managers do not know that effective time management is proper ordering of our values, goals and objectives and spending time on those commanding our priority. Thus time management becomes a stressor to them.

o) Middle Age Crisis: Stress as an influence of stressor is directly traceable to persons who have reached middle age and failed to achieve career goals experienced by a large number of managers and professional people. According to Levinson in Hall (2021), “from age forty-five, a man once again questions his life. But the questioning probes the past as well as the future.” What have I accomplished?, by the age of forty which brings to an end early adulthood and brings in middle life, most men have enough data to make a realistic assessment of their success and failure pattern in life and when the assessment is not in their favour, it turns into a stressor and begins to influence their life. The thought of this most times makes most managers to resort to things like alcoholism to offset their worries.

The Various Ways of Coping with Stress

Stress is generally described as the non-specific response of the body to any demand made upon it by both external and internal stimulus events (stress producing factors) technically called stressors. Stress is a pervasive situation that can be experienced at work, at home, at school even at play. According to Otieno (2018), some of the variants of stress include work, job or occupational stress, marital stress, executive stress, social stress, and economic stress. Most at times stress is noticed to produce adverse effects on the person or individual and their performances. In view of the predominantly detrimental effects of stress, there is need to take decisive and positive measures to curtail stress. One of the aims of this study is to review and discuss some of the methods of reducing and coping with stress.

Relaxation Techniques

Relaxation is a condition in which the body attains a state of low emotional and physiological arousal. Relaxation techniques therefore refer to the various methods and processes of inducing relaxation. According to Ezeilo (20015) “relaxation is characterised by reduced heart rate, slow and deeper respiration, absence of tension and nervousness and a feeling of well-being”. Some of the techniques of relaxation are:

A. Tension Scanning: It involves examining yourself from the crown of your head to the toes of your feet to locate tension in any part of your body. It involves concentrating your thoughts and noting your fears, agitations, frustrations, displeasures and unhappiness. Deliberately being aware of the spots and inducing calmness to these spots. This help to reduce tension.

B. Diaphragmatic Breathing: This technique according to Ezeilo (2015) “is called deep breathing exercise which ensures that more oxygen than usual gets to the brain”.

C. Psychoimagination: It is a process of taking an excursion in the imagination to places and situations which one usually finds relaxing and engaging in relaxing activities in the situations confirming the efficacy of this exercise, Arbor (2021) said, ‘The effect of this exercise undertaken through imagination are often similar to the effects of undertaking the exercise physically’.

D. Physical Exercise: According to Rimm and Masters (2019), exercise like jogging, aerobics, swimming, games like tennis, squash, football etc, induces relaxation. Reacting to this assertion, Osgood (2018) said “But there is the danger of overlooking the real cause of their stress if we assume that athletic approach is the only technique we need”. This is true because if our stress is caused by a loss of relationship, for instance, jogging isn’t going to resolve the problem. It is just going to make us feel good for a time.

Systematic Desensitisation

This procedure combines relaxation training and a hierarchy of anxiety producing stimuli to gradually get the person over his or her fear of a specific situation. According to Kipper (2017), ‘Soldiers with fears of airplanes open places and blood brought on by war experiences were treated with systematic desensitization’.

Concept of Stress and Job performance

Stress as a variable has been defined differently. The origin of stress could be traced by Latin word ‘stingere’, which means to draw tight. Osgood (2018), who is often regarded as the father of stress defined it as the general wear and tear of life on the body. Fraser (2014) describes stress as a pathological human response to psychological, human response to psychological, social occupational and/or environmental pressures. The international symposium on society, stress and disease, sponsored by the World Health Organization (2022) adopted as a definition the statement that: “stress is the non-specific response of the organism to any demand made of it.

The body therefore sees stress as a response and not a causative. On administrator stress, Selye (2016) defines it as a response of negative effect such as anger or depression, which

is usually accompanied by other response correlates, which may be psychological (such as high blood pressure) or behavioural (for example truancy). In sum therefore, it can be concluded that job stress is a state of physical mental and emotional instability occasioned by elements in the perceived job role and job setting. Like stress, job satisfaction has been defined in different dimensions by scholars.

Influence of Lack Finance on School Administrator

Education is as old as human existence, and is the most important sector in the development of a nation. Every country's education system are powerful instrument for socio-economic progress without which neither an individual nor a country can achieve professional and economic growth. As such the funds that are made available to the education system are expected to be adequate for the running of the school. School financing in Nigeria was initially left in the hands of the missions that brought and established schools. The first primary school was built at Badagry in 1842. Many other primary schools were established by different missionaries between 1846 and 1929. The first secondary in Nigeria was Church Missionary Society Grammar School founded in 1859 by T. B. Macauley. Many other secondary schools were established between 1859 and 1882 with little or no financial support from the colonial government. It took colonial administrators about 40 years after inception of formal education in Nigeria to indicate strong intention to intervene in educational matters by issuing an ordinance.

Government acquired and opened more schools as the communities began to appreciate western education. By 1970, according to Ogbodo in Peretomode (2014), government acquired all primary and secondary schools from the voluntary agencies. Also in 1972, education which was in the concurrent list according to 1963 constitution was reversed and all the state universities were acquired by the federal government. Governments' financial involvement in the running of the schools has increased tremendously over the years due to radical increase in demand and expansion of the education industry. Today, we have two categories of schools.

Influence of Instructional Supervision on School Administrator

Education according to the National Policy on Education is an instrument "par excellence" which is important for national development (FGN, 2004). Education is also the bedrock of any nations' socio-economic, cultural, religious and political development. However, all the various levels of education (early childhood, pre-primary, primary/basic, post primary /secondary and tertiary), including the educational institutions must be properly administered and managed in order to produce vibrant outputs (students) that will contribute effectively towards national development. This in essence will include attainment of a high level of 'academic excellence' which entails the inculcation of the right type of knowledge, skills, values and attitudes to the learner to enable him function efficiently and effectively within the society, and ensure societal survival (Hall, 2021). This according to Lawrence (2020) can be achieved through a disciplined and committed administrator. To ensure that administrators are highly disciplined and their high productivity achieved in the education sector, this apart from staff development will also

include strengthening schools' instructional supervision to ensure that administrator high productivity and work commitment is guaranteed and enhanced.

Instructional supervision according to Willis (2015) is a helping relationship whereby the supervisor guides and assists the administrators to meet the set targets. This definition describes instructional supervision from the point of establishing the relationship with stakeholders in the school system for the purpose of achieving the set objectives. Similarly, Arbor (2021) describe supervision as a service activity that exists to help administrators do their job effectively. In general, according to Ezeilo (2015) the major function of the supervisor is to assist others to become efficient and effective in the performance of the assigned duties.

Influence of Facilities Procurement and Maintenance on School Administrator

While the planning, design, and construction of the school facility may take two to three years, the management of it will last the entire life cycle of the facility. At the beginning of the twenty-first century, the mean age of a school building in the United States as forty-two years, with 28 percent of school buildings built before 1950. Many of the building materials, furnishings, and equipment will not last half that long and will require constant upkeep, maintenance, and inevitable replacement to defer building obsolescence. The costs of managing school facilities have historically received much less attention than facility planning. The percentage of the operating budget for the maintenance and management of school facilities has steadily decreased, creating a capital renewal crisis as a result of years of deferred maintenance at all levels of education.

Best practice requires that a comprehensive facility maintenance program be established and monitored by the school administrator. The maintenance program often includes several distinct programs, including deferred, preventive, repair/upkeep, and emergency maintenance. Responsibility for facility management is divided between the district office and the school site, with the administrator being the primary administrator responsible for the day-to-day operation of the school, including custodial, food, and transportation services.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the fact that studies rank administrators as the most stressed professionals, Head administrators in Rivers State handle both teaching, instructional programmes and administrative tasks which include: curriculum and instructional programmes, finance and business, staff, students, physical resources and public relations (Olembo, 2015 and Okumbe, 2017). This forces them to work for long hours, encounter new problems and less free time for resting and leisure because their social and emotional times are spent working in school environments that determine their survival.

Based on the experiences of head administrators (administrators) occupational tasks; long working hours, new challenging responsibilities, less leisure time, increase in ill health and being appointed to positions of head administrators without any formal preparations on school management, there was need to establish the influence of stress on school

administrators job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State.

A reasonable population of people believes that stress can lead to low job productivity. This speculation seems very rational but requires an empirical. Stressors such as inadequate salary, lack of fund to run the school, late payment of salary, low prestige in the society, inability to meet up with daily expenses, having much work to do etcetera can all lead to job dissatisfaction among the administrators in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. The school administrators are faced on daily basis with stressors which could affect their job satisfaction and productivity.

In Line with these facts, Eferakeya (2013) rightly observed administrators are dissatisfied with their work as a result of lack of or slow promotion, poor salary structure, lack of school facilities, etc. Port Harcourt metropolis has the presence of oil companies whose workers are well paid. The administrator, who is least paid goes to the same market as these oil workers to compete with market forces. The consequences of such stress cannot be ignored. Most administrators who are under job related stress are usually truants or ineffective while working. The result is usually poor performances on the part of the students. The effect is that such administrators hardly prepare for their job effectively nor do they give enough attention to the students. Against this background, that the researcher seek to investigate the influence of stress in school administrators job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to ascertain influence of stress on administrators' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. determine the extent to which instructional supervision as a stressor of school administrators influence their job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.
2. ascertain the extent facilities procurement and maintenance as stressor influence administrators job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.
3. determine to what extent does lack of finance as a stressor influence school administrators job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were used to guide the study.

1. To what extent does instructional supervision as a stressor of school administrators influence their job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?
2. To what extent does facilities procurement and maintenance as stressors influence school administrators job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?
3. To what extent lack of finance as a stressor influence school administrators job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- H₀₁:** There is no significant difference between the mean opinion ratings of male and female school administrators on instructional supervision as a stressor that influence their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State?
- H₀₂:** There is no significant difference between the mean opinion rating of male and female school administrators on facilities procurement and maintenance as stressors that influence their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant difference between the mean opinion ratings of male and female school administrators on lack of finance as a stressor that influence their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

In carrying out this research, the researcher employed descriptive survey design. Descriptive research gives a clear picture of a situation and it serves as a basis for most researchers in assessing the situation as a prerequisite for drawing conclusion. The population of the study consists of all the administrators, vice administrators and Head of Department in public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. The total population size is two and seventy (270) administrators and vice administrators. The sampling technique that was used for the study was simple random sampling technique. This was drawn by slips of papers. Out of eighteen (18) public secondary schools in the study area, all the students in the selected classes were administered with the instruments. However, the sample size of the study was four hundred (400) persons. The instrument that was used for data collection in the study was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was titled: Influence of stress on school administrator job performance. Questionnaire (ISSAJPQ). The data collected were analysed using weighted mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions The criterion decision rule is that any mean score that was from 2.50 and above was accepted while the mean score that was less

than 2.50 was rejected while the null hypotheses was tested using z-test statistical tool at a significance level of 0.05.level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent does instructional supervision as a stressor of school administrators influence their job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Responses on instructional supervision as a stressor of school administrators influence their job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

S/ N	Questionnaire Items	Responses				N	$\Sigma \bar{X}$	Mean (\bar{X})	Remarks
		SA	A	D	SD				
8.	Lack of instructional supervision will affect administrators' job performance in public secondary schools	180 (720)	165 (495)	30 (60)	25 (25)	400	1300	3.25	Accepted
9.	School administrator stress or over work when ensuring the implementation of the educational mission of a school.	190 (760)	165 (495)	30 (60)	25 (25)	400	1325	3.31	Accepted
10	School administrator stressed when overseeing, equipping and empowering teachers to provide meaningful learning.	185 (740)	170 (510)	35 (70)	10 (10)	400	1330	3.32	Accepted
11	School administrator ensures affective instructional supervision thereby over working himself.	185 (740)	170 (510)	35 (70)	10 (10)	400	1330	3.32	Accepted
12	School administrator conduct frequent observations of classroom instruction and provide feedback.	190 (760)	165 (495)	30 (60)	25 (25)	400	1325	3.31	Accepted
13	School administrator over work when looking for teacher evidence of best practice and student evidence of best practice.	185 (740)	170 (510)	35 (70)	10 (10)	400	1330	3.32	Accepted
14	Instructional supervision job is stressful that it can weigh the school administrator down.	180 (720)	165 (495)	30 (60)	25 (25)	400	1300	3.25	Accepted

Table 1 above indicates that the respondents accepted the view that Lack of instructional supervision will affect administrators' job performance in public secondary schools. The table also reveals that the respondents accepted the point that School administrator stressed when overseeing, equipping and empowering teachers to provide meaningful learning. It was also observed from the table that the respondents accepted the fact that School administrator ensures affective instructional supervision thereby over working

himself. Also, it shows that the respondents accepted the view that School administrator conduct frequent observations of classroom instruction and provide feedback. Also revealed from the table is that the respondents accepted that School administrator over work when looking for teacher evidence of best practice and student evidence of best practice and that Instructional supervision job is stressful that it can weigh the school administrator down.

Research Question 2: To what extent does facilities procurement and maintenance as stressors influence school administrators job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Responses on facilities procurement and maintenance as stressors influence school administrators job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Responses				N	ΣX	Mean (\bar{X})	Remarks
		SA	A	D	SD				
15.	Bad or dilapidated school plants influences the school administrators in their job performance.	165 (600)	195 (585)	30 (60)	10 (10)	400	1315	3.29	Accepted
16.	Schools with building materials, furnishings, and equipment will last long which may influence the school administrators.	180 (720)	165 (495)	30 (60)	25 (25)	400	1300	3.25	Accepted
17.	Cost of managing school facilities receiving less attention from government affects school administrators' job performance.	185 (740)	170 (510)	35 (70)	10 (10)	400	1330	3.32	Accepted
18.	Unplanned school physical environment has great influence on the school administrators' job performance in public secondary schools.	190 (760)	165 (495)	25 (50)	20 (20)	400	1325	3.31	Accepted
19	Lack of maintenance culture for school facilities affect on the school administrators job performance in public senior secondary schools.	180 (720)	165 (495)	30 (60)	25 (25)	400	1300	3.25	Accepted

Table 2 above shows that the respondents accepted the view that bad or dilapidated school plants influences the school administrators in their job performance. The table still indicates that the respondents accepted the point that schools with building materials, furnishings, and equipment will last long which may influence the school administrators. It was observed from the table that the respondents accepted the fact that cost of managing

school facilities receiving less attention from government affects school administrators' job performance. It was still shown from the table that the respondents accepted the view unplanned school physical environment has great influence on the school administrators' job performance in public secondary schools and that lack of maintenance culture for school facilities affect on the school administrators job performance in public senior secondary schools.

Research Question 3: To what extent lack of finance as a stressor influence school administrators job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Responses on how lack of finance as a stressor influence school administrators job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Responses				N	$\Sigma \bar{X}$	Mean (\bar{X})	Remarks
		SA	A	D	SD				
20.	Poor funding affects the school administration job performance in public senior secondary schools.	210 (840)	170 (510)	10 (20)	10 (10)	400	1380	3.45	Accepted
21.	Schools are given adequate imprest to run the public senior secondary schools.	60 (240)	85 (255)	140 (280)	115 (115)	400	890	2.22	Rejected
22.	There is enough money to maintain broken down school facilities.	60 (240)	85 (255)	140 (280)	115 (115)	400	890	2.22	Rejected
23.	Adequate funds are available to hire teachers in science and Arts subjects that are insufficient in any school.	60 (240)	85 (255)	140 (280)	115 (115)	400	890	2.22	Rejected
24.	There are funds to buy adequate instructional materials for the classrooms and laboratories in the school.	80 (340)	70 (210)	125 (250)	120 (20)	400	820	2.05	Rejected
25.	Inadequate funding does not border me as a school Administrator	80 (340)	70 (210)	125 (250)	120 (20)	400	820	2.05	Rejected

Table 3 above reveals that the respondents accepted the view that poor funding affects the school administration job performance in public senior secondary schools. It also indicates that the respondents rejected the fact that Schools are given adequate imprest to run the public senior secondary schools. The table also indicates that the respondents rejected the view that There is enough money to maintain broken down school facilities. It still reveals that the respondents rejected the point that adequate funds are available to hire teachers in science and Arts subjects that are insufficient in any school. Also, the table shows that the respondents rejected the views that there are funds to buy adequate instructional materials for the classrooms and laboratories in the school and inadequate funding does not border me as a school Administrator

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean opinion ratings of male and female school administrators on instructional supervision as a stressor that influence their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis on significant difference between the mean opinion ratings of male and female school administrators in the sources of administrators stress that influence their job performance on public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

Respondents	X	Sd	N	Df	STD Error	P	Z-Cal	Z-Crit	Decision
Male	20.6	5.64	42	120	1.46	0.05	0.10	1.96	accepted
Female	7.08	80	80						

Analysis on table 4 shows that the z-cal (0.10) is less than the z-crit (1.96). So, the calculated t-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significant since it is less than the given critical value of z- ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 2 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that no significant difference between the mean opinion ratings of male and female school administrators on instructional supervision as a stressor that influence their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean opinion rating of male and female school administrators on facilities procurement and maintenance as stressors that influence their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State

Table 5: Z-test Analysis on significant difference between the mean opinion ratings of male and female school administrators in the sources of administrators stress that influence their job performance on public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

Respondents	X	Sd	N	Df	STD Error	P	Z-Cal	Z-Crit	Decision
Male	17.9	5.45	42	120	3.98	0.05	0.03	1.96	accepted
Female	17.9	5.79	80						

Analysis on table 5 shows that the z-cal (0.03) is less than the z-crit (1.96). So, the calculated t-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significant since it is less than the given critical value of z- ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 3 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that no significant difference between the mean opinion rating of male

and female school administrators on facilities procurement and maintenance as stressors that influence their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the mean opinion ratings of male and female school administrators on lack of finance as a stressor that influence their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.

Table 6: Z-test Analysis on significant difference between the mean opinion ratings of male and female school administrators in the sources of administrators stress that influence their job performance on public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

Respondents	X	Sd	N	Df	STD Error	P	Z-Cal	Z-Crit	Decision
Male	12.4	4.00	42						
				120	9.24	0.05	0.10	1.96	accepted
Female	13.7	4.79	80						

Analysis on table 6 shows that the z-cal (0.10) is less than the z-crit (1.96). So, the calculated t-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significant since it is less than the given critical value of z- ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 4 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that no significant difference between the mean opinion ratings of male and female school administrators on lack of finance as a stressor that influence their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State

Discussion of Findings

The study indicated in research question 1 that the respondents accepted the view that Lack of instructional supervision will affect administrators' job performance in public secondary schools. The table also reveals that the respondents accepted the point that School administrator stressed when overseeing, equipping and empowering teachers to provide meaningful learning. It was also observed from the table that the respondents accepted the fact that School administrator ensures affective instructional supervision thereby over working himself. Also, it shows that the respondents accepted the view that School administrator conduct frequent observations of classroom instruction and provide feedback. Also revealed from the table is that the respondents accepted that School administrator over work when looking for teacher evidence of best practice and student evidence of best practice and that Instructional supervision job is stressful that it can weigh the school administrator down.

The study indicated in research question 2 that the respondents accepted the view that bad or dilapidated school plants influences the school administrators in their job performance. The table still indicates that the respondents accepted the point that schools

with building materials, furnishings, and equipment will last long which may influence the school administrators. It was observed from the table that the respondents accepted the fact that cost of managing school facilities receiving less attention from government affects school administrators' job performance. It was still shown from the table that the respondents accepted the view unplanned school physical environment has great influence on the school administrators' job performance in public secondary schools and that lack of maintenance culture for school facilities affect on the school administrators job performance in public senior secondary schools.

The findings of the study revealed in research question 3 that the respondents accepted the view that poor funding affects the school administration job performance in public senior secondary schools. It also indicates that the respondents rejected the fact that Schools are given adequate imprest to run the public senior secondary schools. The table also indicates that the respondents rejected the view that There is enough money to maintain broken down school facilities. It still reveals that the respondents rejected the point that adequate funds are available to hire teachers in science and Arts subjects that are insufficient in any school. Also, the table shows that the respondents rejected the views that there are funds to buy adequate instructional materials for the classrooms and laboratories in the school and inadequate funding does not border me as a school Administrator.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher conclude stressors like instructional supervision, lack finance or funds to run the school, facilities procurement and maintenance influence school administrators job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. The study also deduced that school administrators are faced with instructional programmes and administrative tasks which include: curriculum and instructional programmes and administrative tasks which include: curriculum and instructional programmes, finance and business, staff, students, physical resources and public relations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that:

- 1 The duty of instructional supervision should not be limited to the school administrators to avoid work overload hence it may influence their job performance.
- 2 Government through ministry of education should take seriously the issue of facilities procurement and maintenance to help the school administrators since it influence their job performance.
- 3 Government should provide more enough fund or finance (impress) for the running of schools hence lack of money or finance affect or influence job performance of the school administrators.

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